

Shovelomics: Measuring faba bean root traits in the field

Problem

Root systems and their interactions with soil are crucial for crop performance, through the capture of water and nutrients. These root functions are important for enhancing crop resilience against climate change. However, studying and measuring root systems is more labour intensive compared to the above-ground parts.

Solution

To facilitate the complex study of roots traits, the shovelomics method was developed for faba bean. The method measures root traits on plants sampled with a spade. This relatively simple method involves the assessment of the 3D architecture of the root crown in the top soil and the measurement of a range of interesting root traits (see figure 1).

Benefits and weaknesses

The shovelomics method was developed for high-throughput field phenotyping and is therefore well suited for breeding programmes. The method is limited to the roots extracted in the top ~20 cm of soil. Measurements can be taken at any time from the start of stem extension to flowering. No specialist tools are required.

Practical recommendations

In the field

Five plants should be excavated at each plot or sampling point using a spade, making sure to remove the full root crown to a depth of around 20 cm. The root crowns with soil are then placed in buckets of water to soften the soil; for some soil types, adding a small amount of soap can help. Once the soil has loosened, it should be carefully removed without damaging the roots. Leave the cleaned root samples in water until measurement.

Applicability box

Theme: Faba bean root measurements

Relevance: Shovelomics enables the measurement of root traits and root crown within the top 20 cm of soil.

Best in: moist and soft soils; any time from the start of stem extension to flowering

Measured traits per plant:

root angle (°),
max depth of root system (mm),
surface root dry weight (g),
stem width at soil level (mm),
tap root diameter (mm),
root length and number (mm, #),
epicotyl root number (#),
shoot and root biomass (g)

Required time:

Analysis per plot (5 plants):
approx. 2.5 h

Equipment:

Spade, buckets, water, soap, graduated scale, balance, oven, shovelomics board

In the lab

With the help of a Shovelomics board, measure the following root traits: root angle, max depth of root system, surface root dry weight, stem width at soil level, tap root diameter, root length and number, epicotyl root number, shoot and root biomass. Optionally, nodulation can be assessed by recording the number, size and activity of nodules and assigning a nodulation score, while root dry weight may also be determined if required.

Figure 1: Shovelomics enables the characterisation of below-ground measurements of faba bean root systems.

Further information

This method was developed by ADAS for the Root2Res project. It was adapted from the methods described in BurrIDGE et al., 2016 and BurrIDGE et al., 2020.

- BurrIDGE, J., JOCHUA, C. N., BUCKSCH, A., & LYNCH, J. P. (2016). Legume shovelomics: high-throughput phenotyping of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) and cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* subsp. *unguiculata*) root architecture in the field. *Field Crops Research*, 192, 21-32.
- BurrIDGE, J. D., RANGARAJAN, H., & LYNCH, J. P. (2020). Comparative phenomics of annual grain legume root architecture. *Crop science*, 60(5), 2574-2593.
- Beauchêne, K., Guillem, P., Baxter, C., White, C., Schwalm, H., Oburger, E., Balestrini, R., Sillo, F. (2023). Deliverable 2.1: Phenotyping toolbox - Architectural traits. Available at <https://root2res.eu/home/knowledge-center/>.
- Root2Res. (2024). Shovelomics in Faba Beans: A Practical Guide. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8laHNGr50dg>.

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

Publisher: ADAS

Authors: Charlotte White (ADAS), Christina Baxter (ADAS), Katia Beauchêne (ARVALIS), Camille Harel (ARVALIS)

Contact: charlotte.white@adas.co.uk

Review: Laura Kemper (FiBL), Nina Gallmann (FiBL), Tim George (JHI), Jean-Pierre Cohan (ARVALIS) and Aleš Kolmanič (KIS)

Permalink: <https://zenodo.org/records/17296615>

This practice abstract was elaborated in the Root2Resilience project, based on the EIP AGRI practice abstract format.

© 2025

Root2Resilience: The project is running from September 2022 to August 2027. The overall goal of Root2Resilience – Root phenotyping and genetic improvement for rotational crops resilient to environmental change – is to develop root phenotyping, genetic and modelling tools and use them to define and test innovative genotype ideotypes able to enhance the tolerance to abiotic stress and carbon sequestration in soils

Project website: root2res.eu

Funding

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra
Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Root2Resilience has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101060124. Its work is supported by Innovate UK through the Horizon Europe Guarantee scheme Grant Agreement No. 101060124 and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under grant No. 23.00050.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), European Research Executive Agency (REA) or the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor any other granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The authors and editors do not assume responsibility or liability for any possible factual inaccuracies or damage resulting from the application of the recommendations in this practice abstract.